

USAGE OF CREATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING BIOLOGY

Academic Lyceum of
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute
Nilufar Abdusalomova Shukhrat kizi

Annotation: The article deals with significant information about the science of biology, its importance in human life nowadays. In addition to this, interactive methods and creative ways of teaching biology were highlighted.

Key words: taxonomy, virology, environments, natural resources, elementary education, didactic-methodic goals, Labster's simulations.

Biology is the study of all living things. In fact, the word "biology" comes from the Greek words bios, which means "life," and logos, which means "study". In short, it's the study of all living things. Biologists study the distribution, evolution, function, growth, origin, structure, and taxonomy of species. We're able to understand how our bodies work, how organisms work, and how our cells work. It's the science that tells us everything about what we are. As you may have guessed, biology is a large area of study. It's so broad that there are entire branches of science within biology. Fields like genetics, agriculture, ecology, virology, and even paleontology are all under this umbrella because they all revolve around the same basic principles of biology. Biology is important because it helps us understand the living world around us, including the human body and the interactions between different living organisms and their environments. This knowledge can be applied to fields such as medicine, agriculture, and conservation, and can help us make informed decisions about how to care for our health, protect the environment, and use natural resources sustainably.

The need to analyse, revise and modernize the conditions in teaching in the

frames of our educational system has lately been closely connected with the tendencies to improve elementary education in our country, in accordance with the dynamic social and economic relations. Likewise, in the times of communication revolution it is necessary that ICT is the catalyst of reforms in education, but it is not the key for changes in education. For these reasons it has become obvious that changes in our educational system (introduction and application of the new conception of nine-year elementary education, development of the new curricula and innovated teaching programs) should be preceded by expert and organizational preparations should be directed to didactic-methodic goals, which in schools will create conditions for successful introduction of the major changes in the most important segment – teaching. For this purpose it is necessary to improve the quality of teaching, increase job skills among students, increase access to computers and integrate the use of ICT in all subjects, with special emphasis on science. Thus, the students will be able to think critically, which in turn will help them achieve success in the global knowledge-based economy and support professional development of teachers.

Finding new ways to teach a biology course to 20 or even 200 students can be exhausting, and the subject can feel inaccessible to students, especially when lecturing is the primary teaching method. You don't have to toss lectures, but you can incorporate other creative ways to engage your students. We've identified eight ways to make your biology teaching life in high school or higher education more manageable and fun, whether you're teaching biology online or in person!

1.) Use Interactive Visuals

Interactive visuals can bring otherwise complex concepts to life for a biology student. A study by Learning From Science News found that people had an easier time digesting and engaging with information when visualizing it. “The possibility to access information through clicking, sliding, or zooming-in might provide a more direct and personally meaningful experience of abstract

phenomena and thus facilitate comprehension and learning.” One way to use these visuals is through bite-size 3D animation videos. Labster offers many of these, including this free biology animation on YouTube: “Antigen-Antibody Binding - Why are some blood types incompatible?”

2.) Learn through Storylines

Cognitive psychologist Jerome Bruner’s research suggests that people are 20 times more likely to remember facts if they’re part of a story. Stories are easy to remember because there’s context, and it’s fun. The ease of remembering and level of engagement is why all Labster’s simulations follow a storyline. It’s questionable what the best way to learn about evolution is, but learning with a storyline full of dogs has to be up there! In Labster's evolution simulation , “Evolution: Journey of the canids,” students follow the million-year evolutionary journey of a canid colony as they create random mutations in their DNA.

3.) Use Polls to Encourage Participation

The days of pure lecture are ending, as students require more chances to engage. Polling has many purposes, such as checking students’ understanding, breaking the ice at the beginning of class, and, most importantly, making it fun! Using polling can encourage a two-way conversation between instructors and students. Many free options include Poll Everywhere , Slido , and Google Forms .

4.) Relate Biology to Everyday Life

Biology topics relate to beauty, healthcare, clothing, fuel, and more. Sciencing.com says that biology permeates so many aspects of everyday life, so why not use these examples to teach? Labster's simulation, " Benedict’s Test for Simple Carbohydrates," teaches students about the structure of simple carbohydrates and how they can test for the presence of simple sugars in food samples. This lab is relevant to students’ daily life who are interested in macromolecules and how they relate to nutrition.

5.) Utilize Team-Based Learning

With team-based learning (TBL), students can be introduced to concepts at home and be actively engaged in learning those concepts in class. They can team up to do simulations and answer quiz questions! Labster virtual labs are used with TBL to help students grasp the material and have fun.

6.) Do Interesting Experiments

A biology lesson can be a hands-on experience. Doing interesting experiments can engage students and help them get excited about their learning. Students can extract DNA from fruit like a banana or strawberry, dissect a frog, or examine a fingerprint. Utilize anything that gets their brains going and helps them learn the material.

7.) Host a virtual field trip

Virtual field trips allow students to go to environments they might not otherwise have access to, especially if you're online teaching. It's not every day that students get to use zebras in their learning.

With Labster's trophic levels simulation, "Trophic Levels: Grazer vs. predator." Students will be able to explain the different chains within a food web and relate them to a trophic pyramid by safely guiding a zebra across a crocodile-filled river.

8.) Prep them for a Career

Biological science can help to prepare students for a future STEM career. It'd be helpful to let them pursue that interest by assigning material that aligns with it. Even if they don't know what they're interested in yet as a future career path, you can help them explore options by aligning lessons with various careers. For example, perhaps your student is interested in pharmacology. Labster has a simulation, Counting Cells: Control the epidemic, where students work as pharmaceutical detectives to identify the link between a new drug and a recent epidemic.

As a conclusion it should be noted that Biology plays a vital role in our daily lives, and its impact will only continue to grow in the future. Whether it's

improving our health, feeding the world, or protecting the environment, biology provides us with the tools and knowledge we need to make the world a better place. Utilizing different methods in teaching biology gives great opportunities to our student to learn this subject fast and more.

REFERENCES:

1. Snezana Stavreva Veselinovska USE THE INTERACTIVE WHITEBOARD IN TEACHING BIOLOGY. 5 th International Conference, Faculty of Technical Sciences Čačak, 30–31th May 2014
2. 8 Creative Ways to Teach Biology without Lecturing (labster.com)
3. <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/The-Importance-of-Biology#:~:text=Biology%20is%20important%20because%20it,and%20use%20natural%20resources%20sustainably>
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-importance-of-using-interactive-methods-in-biology-lessons?ysclid=lqxugk73sc125640816>